

Expansion of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa Worship in Odisha with Special Reference to Baladev Vidyabhusan's Contribution

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Abstract: Śrī Vaiṣṇavism spread in different parts of India from the 10th-11th century onwards and it advocated uniformity in the worship of Viṣṇu in different temples of India. In the 16th century, Odisha witnessed another religious development which has often been called the Bhakti movement or neo-Vaiṣṇava movement. It was popularized in Odisha by Sri Caitanya and the *Panacasakhās* (five associates). Before the advent of Caitanya, Kṛiṣṇa did not receive any exclusive devotion in this region; even Jayadev highlighted the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa union with the composition of *Gītagovinda* at *Śrīkṣetra*. The followers of Caitanya placed Rādhā next only to Kṛiṣṇa in prominence. Thus the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa cult with complete devotion to both, gained prominence in the post-*Gajapati* period and held the popular imagination of Odisha in the post-Gajapati period. The approval of classicism of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship by overturning the traditional Gopīnātha cult which had dominance especially in śāsan villages was a challenge of the medieval times. Also, the recognition of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol worship in the scholarly Brahmin community was a very difficult task achieved in that period. In this regard, the contribution of Baladev Vidyabhusan in this field is worth noting. Baladev's Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa classical theory influenced the response to theology in Odisha. Based on Baladev's classical teachings, Sanskrit poets and devotees of Odisha wrote beautiful poems and gave a great impetus to the worship of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa with emphasis on devotional love. This paper analyses the expansion of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa worship, investigates the role of Baladev Vidyabhusan and explores the temples erected for the above-mentioned deities.

Keywords: *Gajapati*, *Mandapa*, Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa, śāsan, Vaiṣṇavism.

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Introduction

The roots of Vaiṣṇavism lay deep in the soil of Odisha and it can be divided into three periods, early, medieval, and modern (Mukherjee 1940: VI). According to Historian Jandunath Sarkar, the diverse religions of Odisha in all ages have tended to gravitate towards and finally merged into Jagannātha worship (Ibid.: IV). The medieval period in the history of Odishan Vaiṣṇavism begins in the eleventh century CE, with the ascension of Ganga ruler Codaganga on the throne of Kalinga. His crowning achievement was the work he began on the eve of his life: the construction of the temple of Jagannātha. The Jagannātha trinity in Puri was well established by the time of another Ganga king Anangbhimadeva III. Codaganga and Anangabhimadeva III espoused the cause of Vaiṣṇavism and with the proverbial zeal of enthusiasts, they erected an immense and gigantic structure as “the magnificent assertion of autocratic devotion”¹. From the 15th century CE, Jagannātha attained the status of the *rāṣṭradevatā* (state deity) under the Suryavamsi Gajapati kings, who ruled over the present region of Odisha between CE 1434-1541. Suryavamsi ruler Kapilendradeva seized the throne in 1434 CE, and his son, Puruṣottamadeva addressed lord *Puruṣottama* as Jagannātha. Both of them owed the throne to the popular belief about Jagannātha’s dispensation in their favour and gratefully patronized the Vaiṣṇava faith and scholars. In 1510 CE, Sri Caitanya, the greatest saint of the Bhakti cult visited Odisha during the reign of Puruṣottamas’ son Prataprudradeva.

Gajapati Puruṣottam Deva (CE 1467-1497) first established 16 śāsan villages for the settlement of high-ranking noble Brahmins. At that time Cuttack, also called as “*Avinaba Vāranāsi Kataka*”, was their capital. Reliable details about the establishment of the said 16 śāsan villages in Cuttack and nearby areas can be found in ‘*Cakodā Pothi*’². Since the 16 śāsan villages were founded by Śrīgopāla worshipper *Gajapati* Puruṣottam Deva, Śrīgopāla has been the main deity of these famous Brahmin śāsans till now. There was no mention of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa Idol worship in these parts even though Caitanya and other saints preached extensively in favour of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa worship. In 1568 CE, before *Kalāpābhāda* (as named in Odia language) – a Muslim General of the Bengal Sultanate under the reigning Suleiman Karrani, but a Brahmin by birth – captured Cuttack and destroyed the Gopāla Temple,

some learned person secretly moved the Śrī Gopāla idol from Cuttack. The popularity of the 16 śāsan villages near Cuttack also declined subsequently. Later, Ramacandra Deva (CE 1568-1600), the first king of the Bhoi dynasty established his capital at Khurda and installed a new temple for Śrī Gopāla in Khurda. He set up 16 śāsan villages in the region of Puri under his control to restore or revive Brahminical religion. As the 16 śāsan villages near Puri were designed on the model of the 16 śāsan villages near Cuttack, the chief deity of these new śāsan villages was Śrīgopāla or Gopinātha. As there is no Bhāgavata Purana support for Rādhā worship and the ruling Brahmin scholars accept the *Bhāgavata Purāna* as the authentic text, the Rādhā idol is nowhere to be seen near Śrīgopinātha idols in the said traditional 16 śāsan villages. Only the Gopinātha idols are established and worshipped in all Brahminical śāsans.

Saint Syamananda and his disciple Rasikananda promoted the dual worship of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa in Odisha first. A king of Odisha who sent Śrī Rādhā idol to Vrindavana is identified with Khurda King Puruṣottam Deva (CE 1601-1623) of the Bhoi dynasty of Odisha³. In the first two decades of the 17th century, Śrī Rasikananda introduced the dual idol worship of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa in Odisha, and possibly under his influence, the said king Purushottam Deva sent Śrī Rādhā idol to Vrindavana for the satisfaction of the Vaiṣṇava Gosvamis, and it was first installed near the idol of Śrī Govindajīu. Later, another Rādhā idol sent from Odisha was installed at Madanagopāla's side. But despite Śrī Rasikananda's life-long campaign in favour of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol worship, the *smārta pandita* or priest group of Odisha did not accept the worship of Rādhā along with Kṛiṣṇa. King Kirvichandra Parusottam of Vardhaman had filled stone in the Markandeya *Sarovar* (pool) in Puri and built a small temple for the idol of Gopinātha-Kṛiṣṇa on the bank of the pool. The said statue and temple are proven to have been built in the early part of the reign of *Gajapati* Birakesari Deva I from the inscription erected there⁴. Here too the absence of Rādhā on the side of Kṛiṣṇa is noticeable. The Gopināthā Temples are found in different parts of Odisha, especially in the coastal districts of the state.

Based on all of the above considerations, it is assumed that the Gopinātha-Kṛiṣṇa idol was commonly worshipped in Odisha till about 1750 CE. Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol worship flourished and became popular in Odisha subsequently through the efforts of Baladev Vidyabhusan, the popular saint and son of Odisha as referred to in section I.

Section- I

As the Vaiṣṇavas of South India were protesting against the idol worship of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa in Vrindavana, during the Vaiṣṇava Conference convened in Jaipur, Rajasthan in 1740, the famous Utkal scholar Baladev Vidyabhusan, with the help of *Govindabhāṣya*, propounded extensively about the introduction of classicism in idol worship. After this, the worship of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols spread rapidly throughout India. Odisha's contribution towards the establishment of the Śrī Rādhā idol in Vrindavana Dham and its classicization was very important. After that, the trend of establishing and worshipping Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols in Odisha seems to have continued.

The contribution of the philosopher Baladev Vidyabhusan in this regard is extraordinary. It is Baladev Vidyabhusan's achievement to establish the Śrī Caitanya-propagated love-devotional religion at the national level as an 'inexhaustible discrimination' by demonstrating the classicality of the worship of the Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol. By producing the famous *Govindabhāṣya* commentary of *Brahmasūtra*, Dashopaniṣad, *Srīmad Bhagavadgīta* and *Viṣṇu-sahasranāma*, he became the founder of a new order of Vaiṣṇavism in the Vaiṣṇava religion, following Shankara, Ramanuja, Nimbarka, Madhva and Ballabhacharya. He is now considered the heir to the Radhamohan *Maṭha* (monastery) at Gopiballabhapur in Medinipur district, West Bengal, which was separated from Odisha in the past, and also the heir of the family of Rasikananda Deva Goswami. According to this tradition, the noble family of Gopiballavapur belongs to the Syamananda community. Devotee Baladev Vidyabhusan was a monk belonging to this Syamananda community.

Baladev Vidyabhusan was born in a village near the famous *Kshirachora Gopinātha Peetha* at Remuna, not far from the modern city of Baleswar in the state of Odisha⁵. At a very young age, he came to Puri to learn Sanskrit and later to learn philosophy from a prominent scholar in Parikud, in the middle of Lake Chilika. While at the theological monastery in Puri, he took initiation into Vaiṣṇavism from Rasikananda Deva Goswami's follower Rādhādamodar and defeated many scholars in ideological discussions. He then went to Vrindavana, where he received the companionship of Viswanātha Chakravarty and other Vaiṣṇava monks. During the stay of Baladev Vidyabhusan in Brahmaputra, monks from the four Vaiṣṇava sects of South India came to Galta near

the capital Jayapur (Jaipur) in the state of Rajputana (Modern Rajasthan) and protested against the worship of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol. At that time, the king of Rajputana was Sawayi Jayasingha, a supreme Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa-devotee. He founded the new capital of the state at Jayapur in 1728 CE. King Jayasingha could not find a satisfactory solution to the ideology of anti-idol worship of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa of the southern Vaiṣṇavas. As a result, he was forced to remove the statue of Śrī Rādhā from the Govindjīu temple in Galta. But that did not end there. King Jayasingha called the monks of Vrindavana to satisfy the Vaiṣṇavas of the south with a correct answer to the classical nature of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship. In Vrindavana, monks from Śrī Kṛiṣṇa-Caitanya community sent *pandit* Baladev Vidyabhusan to establish the truth of the worship of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol by classical discussion with the Vaiṣṇavas of the south at the Galta Govindji temple.

After hearing all the arguments of the opposition of Galta Govindjīu Temple, Baladev demanded one month's time to establish the facts and ideology of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship. During his one-month stay at the Govindjīu Temple, he wrote three commentaries *Brahmasutra*, *Bhagavadgita* and *Dashopanīśad* under the title *Govindabhāṣya*⁶. These three commentaries of Vedānta were accepted by the southern Vaiṣṇava monks. The arguments of the opponents of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship became meaningless in comparison to Vidyabhusan's wonderful scholarship work *Govindabhāṣya*. Later, the remaining idol of Rādhā was re-erected on the left side of Śrī Gobindajīu or Kṛiṣṇa idol and the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol worship was honoured among all the Vaiṣṇava communities of India.

The religious assembly held at the Gobindajīu Temple in Galta with the participation of Baladev Vidyabhusan and the composition of *Gobindabhāṣya*, is estimated to have occurred around 1740 CE.⁷ Researchers estimate that Vidyabhusan was 30 years old at that time. Therefore, the birth of Vidyabhusan dates back to about 1710 CE. Baladev wrote a famous commentary named *Utkalika-Balari* on Rupa Goswami's work *Stabakamala* in 1764 CE. He died at the age of 90. During his long life, he is said to have been the author and commentator of about 24 books. Among them, *Bhagavat's Vaiṣṇavanandini* commentary, *Siddhārtaratna*, Gopāla Tāpini commentary, *Prameya Mukhali*, *Bhaktirasamritsindhu* commentary, *Lalit Madhava* commentary, and *Vidagdha Madhava* commentary are famous. Through his

lifelong practice, Baladev tried to spread the philosophy and ideology of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa cult across the world in the religious Era. The temples erected for worshipping Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa in different parts of Odisha are discussed in the next section.

Section- II

After the classicization of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol worship by *Pandita* Baladev Vidyabhusan at a place called Haripur of Mayurbhanj district, the construction of Sri Radhamohana and Sri Rasikaraya temples stand as monuments of Neo-Vaiṣṇavism in Odisha. The said Haripur village on the banks of the river *Budhābalanga* is now abandoned. Before Baripada was formed as the capital of Mayurbhanj, the said Haripur was its capital. Even though its ruins are visible now, the said temple remains as a silent witness to the fact that it was once one of the centres of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa worship. In this district, Rādhāmohan temple at Baripada town, Gopālajīu *Maṭha* at Jamda village ten miles from Bahalada, Sri Shamaraya Mahaprabhu temple at Karanjia, Banabihārī temple at Takatpur village two miles from Baripada town are symbols of this neo-Vaiṣṇava movement in Odisha.

Vamsibādana temples at Sunhat of Balasore district and Rādhāmohan temples at Mangalpur of Jajpur district are evidence of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa worship in Odisha. The construction period of these temples and sculptures is said to be in the second half of the 18th century CE. The Gopālajīu Temple built by Queen Amrita Kumari in the city of Balangir is one of the symbols of the said Neo-Vaiṣṇava ideology. This temple is the first and oldest temple in Balangir town. The said temple was built in 1872 CE when the kings of the Chauhan clan moved the capital from Patnagarh to Balangir (Senapati 1968: 23). Madana Gopāla temple is said to have been built at the end of the 18th century CE in Lulagarh village located in Bantala police station under Angul district. Madana Gopāla, the deity of this temple, and the idol of Śrī Rādhā installed on his side are revered and worshipped as the supreme deity by the people of the area. Kunjakānta Kṛiṣṇa temple was built in Ambrakunja located in Dhenkanal town and the date of the temple was established as 1917 CE by Dr. Naveen Kumar Sahu⁸.

In that time, the public became intimately familiar with the majesty of Śrī Kṛiṣṇa's Gopālila, and Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols were installed and worshipped in every corner of the country. The traditional painters of this country under the influence of Neo-Vaiṣṇavism excelled in making the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol with beautiful workmanship. The metal Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol and wooden Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol preserved in the State Museum are beautiful examples of Odisha's traditional craftsmanship and idol-making techniques. Not only in temples or in sculptures, but in the houses of the nobles to the cottagers, the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols are painted in villages of Odisha as a reminder of traditional taste and religion. One such beautifully painted picture is preserved in the State Museum.

During the era of widespread Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship, it seems to have established its seat among the tribal *Kandha* community of the country rather than remaining bound among the Brahmin śāsan villages. The Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa temples and idols established and worshipped in the village called Kandhasarla, just 25 kilometres distant from the modern Bhanjnagar city of Ganjam district are worth mentioning in this context. From the name of the said village, its inhabitants can easily be identified. Here, the idols of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa were initially installed and worshipped in a small mud hut, and now the idols have been re-installed and worshipped in a beautiful brick temple.

During the peak of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idol worship, Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols were made not only of stone, metal or wood, but also of precious ivory. One such beautifully crafted pair of ivory-carved Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa idols, now isolated from Odisha, is worshipped and enshrined in the temple in the Dasarathipur śāsan village (now in Andhra Pradesh), which was established by the Paralakhemundi dynasty. Dasarathipur śāsan village is just four kilometres south of Paralakhemundi town. The last interesting glimpse of Śrī Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idol building and worship in the modern period can be found at Śrī Rādhā Gobinda temple, the home deity of Dr. Satyanarayan Rajguru of Parlakhemundi town. Dr. Rajguru's grandfather, *Pandita* Madhusudan Rajguru, built a temple in front of their residence for the said Rādhā Gobinda, in the first decade of the 20th century and installed Sri Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa twin idols in it, which continues to be worshipped till this day.

Conclusion

Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa's divine love appears to have been widely accepted by all communities of the society; as a result, many writers, saints and scholars of Sanskrit and Odia literature began to write regarding Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa in their work since the mid-eighteenth century up to the twentieth century CE. Poets Nityananda and Raghunath Tirtha composed *Sbri Krishnalilamrita* and *Mukundavilas* respectively, interpreting Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa Premlila and making Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa worship popular in Odisha. Kabichandra Kamallochan's grandfather Govinda composed the *Samriddhamadhava Natak* based on the *Gitagovinda*. Ramchandra Khadgaraya was able to popularize the theme of divine love by composing the poem *Narahari Charitam*. Under the influence of the Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa age and inspired by the established ideas of his grandfather, poet Kamallochana composed three poems on Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa divine love. Like his grandfather Govinda, he was also a follower of Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa dual idols worship and a supporter of Gaudiya views and that is why he has sung in respect of Sri Gauracandra or Sri Caitanya in his Sanskrit works *Sangita Chintamani* and *Gitamukunda*. Many Odia writers interpreted Rādhā-Kṛiṣṇa *līla* in their poems inspired by the works of Kabibhusan Govinda and Kabichandra Kamallochan. Among them, poet Laxmana Bhatt, Kabibhushan Gopinath Patra, Lokanatha Tripathi and Kabiratna Purohit Sadashiv Udgata are considered as the frontliners. Raghunath Das' book *Kalanirnaya*, and Gadadhar Rajguru's book *Kalasara* first discussed the diversity of Vaisnava *Ekadasi* by following the *Haribhakti Vilasa*. Mahamahopadhyay Krushna Mishra, one of Odisha's most famous memoirists, compiled a special chapter called *Vaisnava Prakarana* in the book *Kalasarvasva*.

Notes

1. Hunter, 1872, 100.
2. Mahapatra, 1969, 18.
3. Mahapatra, 1969, 180.
4. Mahapatra, 1969, 273.
5. Acharya, 1969, 418.
6. Acharya, 1994, 111.
7. Acharya, 1994, 419.
8. Senapati, 1972, 62.

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